

Appendix A: Energy-phase matrices and energy-resolved pulse profiles of observations

Here we show the general evolution of V 0332+53 pulse profiles for all the different *NuSTAR* observations examined in this paper. Energy-phase colour matrices offer a quick-look view of the pulse shape in the full 3–70 keV energy band. The profiles have been aligned using as reference the phase of minima of the first harmonic.

Appendix B: Harmonic decomposition: energy-dependence for the fundamental and the second harmonic amplitudes

As shown in Ferrigno et al. (2023), the PF is the simplest scalar used to physically describe the overall strength of the pulsed emission over the total emission. When the pulsed profile is decomposed in its Fourier terms, the single amplitudes might not have a direct correspondence with physical quantities. Nonetheless, it is worth investigating if the complex structure we observed in the PF spectrum might be determined only from the trend of the fundamental, and what is the specific contribution for the second harmonic at the same time. With the same methods we used to describe the PF trend in the general PF spectra, we repeated the same steps to describe the amplitudes of the fundamental and the second harmonic (there remains too little power and statistics to attempt any description of the higher harmonic components). We comparatively show these two amplitudes side by side in Fig. B.1 and B.2. We restrict this comparative analysis only for the first four observations, as the harmonic amplitudes of the low-statistics observations result too poorly determined.

As expected, the general PF trend is mostly carried out by the amplitude of the fundamental, which by itself, reproduces the double-peaked pattern and its essential variability for the different observations. The amplitude of the second harmonic does not follow the trend of the fundamental only for the brightest observation (ObsID 802), where there is a drop. In all the remaining observation, the second harmonic amplitude displays a very similar pattern to the fundamental shape.

A comprehensive summary of the best-fitting results, both for the PF spectrum and the energy-dependent amplitudes of the fundamental and second harmonic is shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Fig. A.1. Energy-phase colour maps and energy-selected pulse profiles for ObsIDs 806.

Fig. A.2. Energy-phase colour maps and energy-selected pulse profiles for ObsIDs 808.

Appendix C: Spectral fit results

We present here the best-fitting results from fitting the phase-averaged spectra of observations 802, 804, 806, and 808 with the models described in Sect. 4 in Tables C.1, C.2, C.3, and C.4, respectively. Data, residuals (for all models) and the best-fitting *wings* model superimposed on the data are shown in Fig. C.1.

Appendix D: Corner plots of the Wings model

Fig. A.3. Energy-phase colour maps and energy-selected pulse profiles for ObsIDs 810.

Fig. A.4. Energy-phase colour maps and energy-selected pulse profiles for ObsIDs 902.

Fig. A.5. Energy-phase colour maps and energy-selected pulse profiles for ObsIDs 904.

Fig. B.1. Energy-dependent amplitudes (first harmonic: left panels; second harmonic: right panels), best-fitting models and residuals for ObsID 802 (upper panels) and 804 (lower panels).

Fig. B.2. Energy-dependent amplitudes (first harmonic: left panels; second harmonic: right panels), best-fitting models and residuals for ObsID 806 (upper panels) and 808 (lower panels).

Fig. C.1. Phase-averaged spectral fitting of ObsIDs 802, 804, 806 and 808. a) Modelling the fundamental cyclotron line with one Gaussian feature in absorption and two Gaussian features in emission representing the blue and red peaks or *wings* with the values derived from the phase-resolved analysis were used as Gaussian priors, described in Sect. 4.1 b) Residuals of (a), c) residuals of modelling the line with two Gaussian features in absorption, d) residuals of modelling the line with just one Gaussian feature in absorption.

Table C.1. Best-fitting spectral results for ObsID 802.

Parameter	Units	<i>wings</i>	<i>one gabs</i>	<i>nested gabs</i>
		Best-fitting Values		
E_{RW}	keV	24.02±0.08	—	—
σ_{RW}	keV	1.08±0.07	—	—
N_{RW}	×10 ⁻³	1.6±0.3	—	—
E_{BW}	keV	31.28 ^{+0.12} _{-0.10}	—	—
σ_{BW}	keV	2.19 ^{+0.14} _{-0.10}	—	—
N_{BW}	×10 ⁻³	3.0 ^{+0.6} _{-0.4}	—	—
E_{Fe}	keV	6.485±0.010	6.488±0.011	6.492±0.011
σ_{Fe}	keV	0.338±0.012	0.344±0.014	0.308±0.014
N_{Fe}	×10 ⁻³	11.4±0.4	11.7±0.5	9.8±0.4
E_{Cyc1}	keV	28.20 ^{+0.09} _{-0.07}	27.84±0.03	27.79±0.02
σ_{Cyc1}	keV	3.99±0.04	3.83±0.03	4.50 ^{+0.14} _{-0.08}
τ_{Cyc1}	keV	14.8 ^{+0.4} _{-0.3}	12.65±0.12	10.9 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}
σ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	—	2.35 ^{+0.13} _{-0.09}
τ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	—	2.7 ^{+0.6} _{-0.3}
E_{Cyc2}	keV	51.68±0.16	51.89±0.16	51.72±0.17
τ_{Cyc2}	keV	18.7±0.4	17.8±0.5	18.0±0.4
E_C	keV	11.51±0.06	11.60±0.06	11.05±0.14
E_F	keV	8.15±0.04	8.06±0.04	7.80±0.05
E_W	keV	9.62±0.15	9.46±0.15	12.2 ^{+0.5} _{-0.3}
Γ		0.497±0.008	0.504±0.008	0.396 ^{+0.018} _{-0.022}
N_{PL}		0.375±0.005	0.380±0.006	0.317±0.010
C_{cal}		0.9884±0.0008	0.9884±0.0007	0.9884±0.0008
Cstat/dof		530/385	687/391	493/389

Notes. E_{RW} , σ_{RW} and N_{RW} are line position, sigma and normalization (in units of photons/cm²/s) for the red wing line. E_{BW} , σ_{BW} and N_{BW} are line position, sigma and normalisation (in units of photons/cm²/s) for the blue wing line. E_{Fe} , σ_{Fe} and N_{Fe} are line position, sigma and normalization (in units of photons/cm²/s) for the iron emission line. E_{Cyc1} , σ_{Cyc1} , and τ_{Cyc1} are line position, width and strength of the **gabs** component of the fundamental cyclotron line. σ_{Cyc1N} and τ_{Cyc1N} are width and strength of the nested **gabs** at the fundamental cyclotron line energy. E_{Cyc2} , σ_{Cyc2} , and τ_{Cyc2} are line position, width and strength of the **gabs** component of the second harmonic cyclotron line. E_C , E_F , E_W , Γ , and N_{PL} are the cut-off energy, the folding energy, the smoothing width, the photon-index and component normalisation (in units of photons/keV/cm²/s at 1 keV) of the newhcut continuum component (see [Burderi et al. 2000](#)). C_{cal} is a multiplicative constant for the FPMB dataset (this constant is fixed to 1 for the FPMA dataset).

Table C.2. Best-fitting spectral results for ObsID 804.

Parameter	Units	<i>wings</i>	<i>one gabs</i>	<i>nested gabs</i>
		Best-fitting Values		
E_{RW}	keV	$23.677^{+0.012}_{-0.016}$	—	—
σ_{RW}	keV	$1.725^{+0.016}_{-0.008}$	—	—
N_{RW}	$\times 10^{-3}$	2.61 ± 0.11	—	—
E_{BW}	keV	31.42 ± 0.04	—	—
σ_{BW}	keV	2.271 ± 0.007	—	—
N_{BW}	$\times 10^{-3}$	1.63 ± 0.10	—	—
E_{Fe}	keV	6.463 ± 0.009	6.470 ± 0.012	6.456 ± 0.013
σ_{Fe}	keV	0.3578 ± 0.0013	$0.363^{+0.021}_{-0.017}$	$0.295^{+0.019}_{-0.016}$
N_{Fe}	$\times 10^{-3}$	5.8 ± 0.2	$5.9^{+0.3}_{-0.2}$	4.6 ± 0.2
σ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	2.39 ± 0.06	
τ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	4.06 ± 0.20	
E_{Cyc1}	keV	28.31 ± 0.03	28.15 ± 0.03	$27.89^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$
σ_{Cyc1}	keV	3.828 ± 0.010	3.64 ± 0.03	5.71 ± 0.07
τ_{Cyc1}	keV	15.09 ± 0.02	12.39 ± 0.13	17.3 ± 0.5
E_{Cyc2}	keV	51.64 ± 0.08	$51.83^{+0.22}_{-0.19}$	$50.97^{+0.22}_{-0.19}$
τ_{Cyc2}	keV	21.92 ± 0.02	$21.4^{+0.8}_{-0.7}$	$19.7^{+0.8}_{-0.6}$
E_{C}	keV	13.28 ± 0.03	13.21 ± 0.05	$17.4^{+0.4}_{-0.5}$
E_{F}	keV	8.255 ± 0.018	8.22 ± 0.04	$6.80^{+0.13}_{-0.10}$
E_{W}	keV	10.484 ± 0.010	9.81 ± 0.14	28^{+1}_{-2}
Γ		0.530 ± 0.002	0.538 ± 0.006	0.415 ± 0.019
N_{PL}		0.1788 ± 0.0008	0.181 ± 0.002	$0.149^{+0.004}_{-0.003}$
C_{cal}		0.9787 ± 0.0014	0.9787 ± 0.0009	0.9787 ± 0.0009
Cstat/dof		583/375	721/381	488/379

Notes. See notes in Table [C.1](#) for parameter definitions.

Table C.3. Best-fitting spectral results for ObsID 806.

Parameter	Units	Best-fitting Values		
		<i>wings</i>	<i>one gabs</i>	<i>nested gabs</i>
E_{RW}	keV	24.65±0.08	—	—
σ_{RW}	keV	1.56±0.03	—	—
N_{RW}	$\times 10^{-3}$	2.0±0.3	—	—
E_{BW}	keV	30.51±0.07	—	—
σ_{BW}	keV	1.90±0.03	—	—
N_{BW}	$\times 10^{-4}$	7.5±1.0	—	—
E_{Fe}	keV	6.501±0.016	6.504±0.014	6.474±0.015
σ_{Fe}	keV	0.310±0.008	0.308 ^{+0.024} _{-0.018}	0.32±0.02
N_{Fe}	$\times 10^{-3}$	2.98±0.14	2.96±0.17	3.05±0.18
E_{Cyc1}	keV	28.26±0.06	28.38±0.03	28.22 ^{+0.05} _{-0.04}
σ_{Cyc1}	keV	3.58±0.03	3.70±0.03	5.52±0.08
τ_{Cyc1}	keV	14.52±0.07	12.69±0.17	19.6±0.7
σ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	—	2.17±0.08
τ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	—	3.2±0.2
E_{Cyc2}	keV	51.00±0.08	50.98±0.17	50.02±0.20
τ_{Cyc2}	keV	21.93 ^{+0.15} _{-0.18}	22.2±0.7	20.5±0.9
E_C	keV	14.00±0.05	13.95±0.04	20.3 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}
E_F	keV	8.50±0.05	8.55±0.05	6.82 ^{+0.22} _{-0.19}
E_W	keV	8.70±0.07	8.42 ^{+0.19} _{-0.15}	25 ⁺¹ ₋₂
Γ		0.552±0.004	0.555±0.006	0.515±0.008
N_{PL}		0.1197±0.0009	0.1203±0.0015	0.1116±0.0018
C_{cal}		0.9777±0.0014	0.9777±0.0010	0.9777±0.0011
Cstat/dof		543/369	670/375	523/373

Notes. See notes in Table [C.1](#) for parameter definitions.

Table C.4. Best-fitting spectral results for ObsID 808.

Parameter	Units	<i>wings</i>	<i>one gabs</i>	<i>nested gabs</i>
		Best-fitting Values		
E_{RW}	keV	$24.802^{+0.011}_{-0.006}$	—	—
σ_{RW}	keV	$3.102^{+0.005}_{-0.007}$	—	—
N_{RW}	$\times 10^{-4}$	<2.3	—	—
E_{BW}	keV	$33.422^{+0.005}_{-0.012}$	—	—
σ_{BW}	keV	1.42 ± 0.03	—	—
N_{BW}	$\times 10^{-4}$	$2.3^{+0.8}_{-0.6}$	—	—
E_{Fe}	keV	$6.357^{+0.011}_{-0.006}$	$6.35^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$	6.357 ± 0.008
σ_{Fe}	keV	$0.2677^{+0.0029}_{-0.0014}$	$0.28^{+0.08}_{-0.04}$	0.266 ± 0.003
N_{Fe}	$\times 10^{-4}$	6.3 ± 0.9	$6.4^{+1.2}_{-0.9}$	6.2 ± 0.4
E_{Cyc1}	keV	29.01 ± 0.03	28.72 ± 0.05	28.72 ± 0.03
σ_{Cyc1}	keV	$3.374^{+0.019}_{-0.009}$	3.19 ± 0.05	3.200 ± 0.010
τ_{Cyc1}	keV	$13.171^{+0.073}_{-0.015}$	12.1 ± 0.2	12.070 ± 0.015
σ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	—	1.357 ± 0.002
τ_{Cyc1N}	keV	—	—	0.0755 ± 0.0006
E_{Cyc2}	keV	52.47 ± 0.03	$52.4^{+0.5}_{-0.4}$	52.42 ± 0.08
τ_{Cyc2}	keV	$24.65^{+0.05}_{-0.04}$	24^{+2}_{-2}	24.51 ± 0.07
E_{C}	keV	$15.937^{+0.022}_{-0.017}$	15.85 ± 0.07	15.86 ± 0.02
E_{F}	keV	8.24 ± 0.03	8.26 ± 0.08	8.265 ± 0.009
E_{W}	keV	$7.61^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	7.3 ± 0.3	7.353 ± 0.011
Γ	0.669	± 0.004	$0.668^{+0.006}_{-0.008}$	0.6695 ± 0.0004
N_{PL}		0.0451 ± 0.0005	$0.0451^{+0.0006}_{-0.0008}$	0.04519 ± 0.00018
C_{cal}		0.9766 ± 0.0020	0.9766 ± 0.0018	0.977 ± 0.005
Cstat/dof		330/322	380/328	374/326

Notes. See notes in Table [C.1](#) for parameter definitions.

Fig. D.1. Corner plots of the Wings model for ObsID 802

Fig. D.2. Corner plots of the Wings model for ObsID 804

Fig. D.3. Corner plots of the Wings model for ObsID 806

Fig. D.4. Corner plots of the Wings model for ObsID 808